

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF CANCER DYNAMICS UNDER CHEMOTHERAPY

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Abstract

Sensitivity analysis of the dynamics of various interacting cells in the chemotherapy mathematically modelled by a set of four ordinary nonlinear differential equations studied. Painleve property analysis for ordinary differential equations is used for the sensitivity analysis and found there are two control parameters associated with the dynamics. These two control parameters related to the immunity cell population in the competition between healthy cells and cancer cells. The inter relationship between two control parameters reported. Finally Interleukin-7 (IL-7) for boosting immunity in combination with Chemotherapy is suggested for better therapy for cancer cure.

Keywords:- Sensitivity, dynamics, chemotherapy, Painleve property, parameters, immunity cell, Interleukin-7, necrotic, proliferation

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1. Introduction

Cancer refers to any one of a large family of diseases characterised by the development of abnormal cells that divide uncontrollably and have capacity to infiltrate and destroy normal tissue. Cancer begins when cells develop errors in their DNA that lead cells to grow and divide uncontrollably and go on living even when other cells would die. These accumulating cells form a tumor. Tumor is a collection of abnormally mutated cells with capacity to surpass the inherent tumor inhibiting mechanisms like tumor suppressive genes or immune response of that organism[1] Tumor is either solid type or cancer of blood like leukemia. Tumor can be non spreading type or spreading type. Micro-environment of

tumor has three layers, living cells, dormant cells or quiescent cells and dead cells. The living cells that are actively multiplying are called proliferating cells formed the outer layer of tumor whereas, dead cells formed by natural death or apoptosis formed the necrotic core of the tumour . In between outer layer and inner core formed by quiescent cell that have capacity to become proliferating cell when sufficient oxygen and nutrients are available [1],[2],[3],[4].

Tumor-immune interaction [1],[2],[3],[4] is controlled by protein-protein interactions of many cells like, macrophages, natural killer cell, cytokines T cells, helper cells, regulatory cells, dendritic cells, memory cells etc. These cells interact activating immune response that tries to restrict tumor growth, all these cells derived from the myeloid progenitors and lymphoid progenitors by differentiation. Another group of four cells are drug-sensitive cells , drug-resistive cells, hormone dependent cells and hormone independent cells. The activation of immune system against tumor growth are two types [1],[2],[3],[4], Innate immune action and adoptive immune action. Innate immune action is rapid response called phagocytosis .The substance that activate immune action and production of respective antibodies are called antigens that are mainly proteins , that are unique for each pathogen. Some of the immune cells like dendritic cells and macrophages use receptors to identify antigens present in the surface of the pathogens and cancer cells [1],[2],[3],[4]

Cytokines are a type of proteins able to control growth, [3],[4],[5]mutation , suppression and activation of immune cells like cytotoxic T cells , macrophages etc . Some of the cytokines like $TGF-\beta$, $IL - 23$ having pro-tumor and anti-tumor properties like tumor inhibition, invasion, and metastasis . These nonlinear dynamics control tumor-infiltrating leukocytes (TILs) into the tumor micro-environment like proliferation and activation of immune cells are very complex signalling pathways.

The general progression of cancer cells can be classified as cellular level and macroscopic level. At the cellular level cancer cells undergo fast multiplication and cell cycle (growth in size , make copies of their genetic material DNA ,divide to form new cells) deregulate without control. When a cancer cell encounters with an immune cell then cytokine activated results destruction or inhibition or survival the cancer cell . The survived cancer cell generally very aggressively proliferated. Cancer cell, host cell, and immune cells form a nonlinear dynamics of competition for share the available oxygen and nutrients for their survival [3],[4],[5].

At the macroscopic level as the tumor grows that moves gradually along with blood stream, that reduce the rate of growth of tumor. When tumor growth controlled by availability of resources like oxygen , nutrients etc , tumor moves along with blood circulatory system and reach other areas of the body. [4],[5].

Following are the therapies used to restrict the tumor growth and gradually eradicate the tumor,[3],[4],[5]. These therapies are classified in terms of their mode of action on the management of tumor shrinkage and eradication.

- i. Chemotherapy, in which one or more therapeutic drugs administered .ii. Immunotherapy, use one or more anti-angiogenesis agents to restrict blood vessel development in tumour.
- iii. Radio therapy , use radiation
- iv. Hormone therapy, in which production of hormone in the body is regulating by hormones or other agents
- v, Miscellaneous therapy, like stem cell therapy, nano medicine mediator therapy, gene therapy, radioviro therapy etc
- vi, Combination therapy, use proper combination of above therapies in suitable intervals .

The term “Chemotherapy” was first used by German chemist Paul Ehrlich [1],[3] who was investigating the medical use of arsenicals in 1900s. Chemotherapy is used to inhibit cell proliferation and tumor cell rapid multiplications so controls invasion, metastasis (progress of tumor from initial state to advanced state along with changing location of the body), cell signal transduction, differentiation, apoptosis, angiogenesis (development of vascular network in the tumor) and growth factor modulations. New methods like molecular targeted therapy on the pathways, selectively inhibiting growth by targeting cell signalling or angiogenesis, blocking protein degradations etc are used in chemotherapy [3],[4],[5]. Different chemotherapy drugs target at different stages of the cell cycle, that way one drug different from other. So generally combination of two or more drugs are selected with proper dosage used for administration. Drug can be given intravenously, subcutaneously, intramuscularly, or orally, generally intravenous is adopted because absorption rate is almost 100%. Chemotherapy then radiation also selected to reduce the size of tumor. There are around five hundred types of chemotherapy drugs are available and almost all of them having side effects. Some drugs help cancer cell-lysis by promoting cell-cycle arrest, others help drug induced ligand-receptor binding that promoting immune cell to kill cancer cell directly. In general chemotherapeutic agent restricting the rapid cell cycle like growth inhibition, cell mutation and variations in the carrying capacity.

There are many types of mathematical models are known [3],[4],[5]. Skipper, Schabel and Wilcox reported a chemotherapeutic model in 1964, according to that the cancer cell-lysis rate is proportional to tumor growth [6],[7],[8]. Three cell-based model for general dynamics of cancer, model for dynamics of drug resistance of cells, model for dynamics of metastasis, model for cell-cycle variations and transitions and model for leukemia. Mathematical modelling of dynamics of tumor may give more insight about the evolution and reactions to the drug of different cells during a therapy. There are many types of cells and parameters controlling the dynamics of tumor in the microenvironment and

interactions are very complex nonlinear types dynamics. When takes into consideration of essential types of cells and the parameters mathematical models can be simplified to three or more dimensional types system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations. Cell population having proliferation, apoptosis, cell transition , competition between same type as well as different types cells for nutrients and oxygen etc. These competitions are like that of predator-prey type having nonlinear dynamics [9].In general the essential variables in a four dimensional model [5]are $H(t)$ the healthy cell without tumor , $C(t)$ the cancer cell , $I(t)$ the immune cell and $U(t)$ the drug concentration . Their interactions controlled by some essential parameters like $a(t)$ the fractional cell-kill rate due to therapy, $b(t)$ the reciprocal carrying capacity, $c(t)$ competition rate between cells, $d(t)$ the death rate or depletion rate, $r(t)$ the growth rate , $m(t)$ the mutation or cell transition rate, , $d_0(t)$ the elimination or depletion rate of therapeutic agent from the tumour site.

One of the standard mathematical model chemotherapy [5],[10] under drug administration of four dimensional nonlinear system of ordinary differential equations (NODEs) is ,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = r_2 H(1 - b_2 H) - c_4 HC - a_1 \{1 - \exp(-U(t))\} H, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = r_1 C(1 - b_1 C) - c_2 IC - c_3 HC - a_2 \{1 - \exp(-U(t))\} C, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = s + \frac{\rho IC}{(\alpha + C)} - c_1 IC - d_0 I - a_3 \{1 - \exp(-U(t))\} I. \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dU}{dt} = -d_0 U(t) + u(t), \quad (4)$$

where $u(t)$ the drug input rate, a_i is drug effect, r_i quantify the growth rate, b_i is reciprocal carrying capacity , c_i competition rate, d_0 death rate, α the immune threshold rate, s is influx rate, ρ is immune response rate. If no drug administration , then $\frac{dH}{dt} = \frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{dU}{dt} = 0$.

The non dimensional form [5]of above set of equations (1)-(4) are,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = H(1 - H) - c_4HC - HG_1(U,t), \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = rC(1 - bC) - c_2IC - c_3HC - CG_2(U,t), \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = 1 + \frac{\rho IC}{(1+C)} - c_1IC - d_0I - IG_3(U,t), \quad (7)$$

where

$$U(t) = U_0\{\exp(-d_0t)\}, \quad (8)$$

and $U_0=U(0)$ denotes some time after termination of drug administration and $G_i(U,t)$ is $a_i[1 - \exp(-U(t))]$, $i=1,2,3$

The interaction between these cells are very complex types of nonlinear dynamics. The term c_1IC denotes the competition between Immune cell $I(t)$ and Cancer cell $C(t)$ as Immunity cells population varies and c_2IC denotes the competition between Immune cells $I(t)$ and Cancer cells $C(t)$ when cancer cell population $C(t)$ varies. The term c_3HC denotes the competition between healthy cell $H(t)$ and cancer cell $C(t)$ when cancer cell population $C(t)$ varies. The term c_4HC denotes the competition between healthy cell $H(t)$ and cancer cell $C(t)$ when cancer cell population $C(t)$ varies. The parameters r_i denotes tumor growth rate in association with immune cell $I(t)$, and influx rate is s . The parameter ρ denotes immune threshold level.

There are several nonlinear methods are known for the study of the tumor dynamics system like phase plain technique[11],[12],[13], Lyapunov exponents analysis [10],[14], equilibrium point analysis [5], centre-manifold theorem [15], small-gain theorem [16], singular perturbation method [17], etc. [18]-[25].

In this study, the sensitivity analysis of the dynamics of above mathematical models are studied using Painleve Property analysis (PPA) of nonlinear dynamical system. In the PPA of nonlinear dynamical system linear equations

having no contribution in the dynamics and so equation (4) neglected in the following analysis. Results are compared with other studies .

2. Stability Analysis by Painleve Property Analysis (PPA) of Nonlinear Ordinary Differential Equations, by ARS Algorithm.

Sensitivity analysis by Painleve property analysis (PPA) of dynamical system modelled as a system of ordinary differential equations by ARS algorithm developed by Ablowitz ,Ramany and Segur is the following . Consider a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) of the form

$$\frac{du_i}{dt} = F_i(u^1, u^2, \dots, u^n), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (9)$$

Then we are searching for dominant behaviour of the solutions in the neighbourhood of a movable singularity of the form

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i}, \quad \text{where } \tau = (t_0 - t) \quad (10)$$

Then there are three steps for the ARS algorithm;

Step 01

Substitute equation (10) in (9) and find all possible values ρ_i , for which two or more leading ordered terms in each equation balance each other, and the rest can be ignored for each such choice of the ρ_i . Also find all possible values of α_i .

Step 02

In step 02 , keep only the leading ordered balancing terms of step 01 and ignore rest and substitute

$$u^i = \alpha_i \tau^{\rho_i} (1 + \gamma_i \tau^r) \quad (11)$$

All product terms of γ_i are to be omitted, then system reduced to

$$Q(r) \cdot \gamma = 0, \quad \text{where } \gamma = (\gamma_1 \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n). \quad (12),$$

Where $Q(r)$ is a $(n \times n)$ matrix in which r entering only in its diagonal elements, almost linearly. Then find the roots of the determinant of

$$\text{Det } Q(r) = 0, \tag{13}$$

These values of r are called resonances. Resonance determines the number of arbitrary constants exist in the system of ODEs (2.01). Resonance $r = -1$ is related to the location of the one free constant, namely t_0 the point of the singularity and that always appear in the roots of (13).

The resonance $r = 0$ corresponds to the coefficient of one of the the leading ordered terms being arbitrary. Any resonance with real valued and $r > 0$ but not an integer indicates at $t = t_0$ is a movable singularity.

Evaluate all possible distinct $(n - 1)$ nonnegative and real valued integer resonances. Less than $(n - 1)$ nonnegative and real valued distinct integer resonances implies system has no PP property.

3. Sensitivity Analysis of Chemotherapy Modelled Equations.

Simplified form of (1)-(4) are, (14)

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = r_2 H - r_2 b_2 H^2 - c_4 HC, \tag{15}$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = r_1 C - r_1 b_1 C^2 - c_2 IC - c_3 HC, \tag{16}$$

$$\alpha \frac{dI}{dt} + C \frac{dI}{dt} = \alpha s + \alpha C + (\rho - \alpha c_1 - d) IC - c_1 IC^2 - \alpha dI, \tag{17}$$

Only balancing dominating consistent terms are,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = -c_4 HC, \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -c_3 HC, \tag{19}$$

and

$$C \frac{dI}{dt} = -c_1 I C^2. \quad (20)$$

Substitute, $H = \alpha \tau^p$, $C = \beta \tau^q$ and $I = \lambda \tau^s$ then the values of $\alpha, \beta, \lambda, p, q$ and s are obtained as,

$$p = q = -1, s = -\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \alpha = \frac{1}{c_3}, \beta = \frac{1}{c_4} \quad \text{and } \lambda \text{ is arbitrary.} \quad (21)$$

For evaluating 'resonance' values of r , substitute ,

$$H = \alpha \tau^p (1 + \gamma \tau^r), C = \beta \tau^q (1 + \delta \tau^r), \text{ and } I = \lambda \tau^s (1 + \eta \tau^r). \quad (22)$$

Yield the resonance equations as

$$r\gamma + \delta = 0, r\delta + \gamma = 0, \text{ and } r\eta + \frac{c_1}{c_4} \delta = 0. \quad (23)$$

Matrix equations corresponds to (23) is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} r & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & r & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{c_1}{c_4} & r \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \delta \\ \eta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

Gives resonance values of r as,

$$r = -1, r = 0 \text{ and } r = +1. \quad (25)$$

All the resonance values of r are integers hence satisfies the Painleve property according to the ARS algorithm, provided $s = -\frac{c_1}{c_4}$ is an nonzero negative integer N like 2,3,.....or

$$\frac{c_1}{c_4} = N, \quad (26)$$

Is a positive integer like 2,3,...,means either both c_1 and c_4 are negative or both are positive number including fractions with condition (26). This implies c_1 and c_4 are the control parameters of the modelled equations . if their values different from (26) produce unstable dynamics of the chemotherapy.

The non-dimensional mathematical modelled equations (5) –(8) can be simplified as,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = H - H^2 - c_4HC, \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = r_0C - r_0b_0C^2 - c_2IC - c_3CH, \quad (28)$$

$$C \frac{dI}{dt} + C \frac{dI}{dt} = 1 + C + (\rho - c_1 - d)CI - c_1IC^2 - dI, \quad (29)$$

Consistent balancing dominating terms according to ARS algorithm are,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = -c_4HC, \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -c_3HC, \quad (31)$$

and

$$C \frac{dI}{dt} = -c_1IC^2. \quad (32)$$

Equations (30) ,(31) and (32) are same as the (18),(19) and (20) respectively and hence the PPA analysis give same results as previous case.

4. Conclusion

Exact reason that starting the cancer is still under investigation, possible contributing factors are identified as, radiation, gene mutation ,lifestyle , certain chemicals , etc. Oncologists use suitable therapeutic methods to restrict The tumor growth and then eradicate that, Survival rate of the cancer patient closely depends on the age, stages of cancer when that diagnose ,and therapeutic methods adopted. For chemotherapy usually combination of two or more drugs are using. There are more than five hundred drugs available ,most of them having side effects . Chemotherapeutic drugs targets all rapidly growing cells in addition to cancer cells, so both cancer cells and healthy cells like blood cells, skin cells, hair follicles, digestive tract etc are affected. After effect of

chemotherapy is, bleeding, constipation or diarrhoea , fatigue, hair loss, nausea etc. Some long lasting side effects are damage to lung tissues ,cardiac problems, infertility, nerve damage, kidney malfunction and risk of second cancer. Most patients need few rounds of chemotherapy with suitable intervals of few days or weeks.

Cancer dynamics depends on many complex interacting factors even then essential factors are cell growth rate of normal or healthy cells, cancer cells, cancer stem cells, drug resistant cells ,immunity cells and concentration of drugs used. Along with many parameters like competition rates ,tumor growth rate, cell-kill rate, immune cell influx ,mutation rate, elimination of drug rate, death rate, tumor microenvironment etc. Suitable number of ordinary differential equations can be used to study the time dependent progression and regression of cancer during and after chemotherapy. Even though such mathematical modelling can not handle all types of variables and parameters that should with two or more essential variables with essential parameters.

In the present study four variables , healthy cell $H(t)$, cancer cell $C(t)$, immunity cell $I(t)$ and therapeutic drug concentration rate $U(t)$ are used. Parameters used are growth rate $r(t)$, death or depletion rate $d(t)$, reciprocal carrying capacity $b(t)$, competition rate between cells $c_i(t)$, drug induced cell-kill rate $a_i(t)$,drug decay rate $d_U(t)$, drug input rate $u(t)$,immune response rate $(\rho(t))$,immune threshold rate $\alpha(t)$ and ,influx rate $s(t)$. The cell killing effect of the therapeutic drug on each cell population is denoted by $a_i[1 - \exp(-kU)]$.

In a sensitivity analysis the variations in the over all dynamics of the system when parameters make small change in values are to be studied. That study reveals the most essential parameters depending on the dynamics of the system, call control parameters. In tumor dynamical system these control parameters indicate when tumor state and tumor high state arises vice versa. . In the present study PPA method is used for sensitivity analysis. PPA method is a standard method for identifying the possibility of integrable and non integrable

states of dynamical system.. System integrable means that dynamics is deterministic and highly stable whereas, non integrable dynamics is unstable in a long time scale when the control parameters varying. In the present study yields two control *arameters* c_1 and c_4 , represent predator- prey type competition rates between two types of cells for oxygen and nutrients in the microenvironments. In which c_1 IC denotes the competition rate between Immunity $I(t)$ cell population and Cancer cell population $C(t)$ when Immunity cell population $I(t)$ varies and c_4 HC denotes the competition rate between Healthy cell population $H(t)$ and cancer cell population $C(t)$ when Healthy cell population varies. The equation (26) denotes these two control parameters c_1 and c_4 related by $c_1 = N c_4$ where $N=2,3,4,\dots$ cannot be either fractions or negative numbers. This implies the competition rate between Immunity cell population $I(t)$ and cancer cell population $C(t)$ must be N times more than competition rate between Healthy cell population $H(t)$ and Cancer cell population $C(t)$ for stable dynamics of chemotherapy . Any variations even that may be a small fractions produce instability in the dynamics of the cancer cell population so other cells populations rates fluctuate that demands repetition of chemotherapy . This observation so far no clinical studies reported .

Above observation denotes the Immunity cell population $I(t)$ must be enhanced so that c_1 the competitions between Immunity cell population $I(t)$ and cancer cell population $C(t)$ must be N times c_4 the competition between healthy cell population $H(t)$ and cancer cell population $C(t)$ for favourable cure in Chemotherapy. For enhancing Immunity cells population $I(t)$ and healthy cells $H(t)$ one of the methods is administration Interleukin-7 (IL-7) as in the case of antiretroviral therapy of HIV infection. Such possibility and its limitations are recently reported in the case of antiretroviral therapy of HIV infection [26]-[29]. So combination of chemotherapy and immunotherapy with IL-7 may be a better option for a better cancer management is the final conclusion of this study.

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